

October 25th-26 2018, BFI Southbank, London

No Time to Wait! Rough Consensus and Running Archives - Collaborative notes

Introduction

This is the collaborative notes document for the third installment of the No Time to Wait symposium series, taking place October 25-26 2018 at BFI Southbank in London.

General Information and Links

- [Event website](#)
 - [Program](#)
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- [Live stream Thu 25 October](#); [Live stream Fri 26 Oct](#)
 - Live stream (Periscope): How we FFV1 panel <https://www.pscp.tv/w/1eaKbVjPVQRKX>
mFollow [@DaleLore](#)
 - [Link to this collaborative document](#)

Note takers:

Johan Oomen. - @johanoomen, Erwin Verbruggen - @erwinverb, Joshua Ng - @joshuatj, Micky Lindlar - @MickyLindlar, Stephen McConnachie - @mcnatch, Reto Kromer @RetoKromer, Ashley Blewer @ablwr

Thursday, October 25th

All times in in BST as per program

A. Luciano and S. McConnachie surveying the conference room - photo credit E. Verbruggen CC-BY

9:15 - Alessandra Luciano: No Time to Wait Introduction

Thanks to everyone!

STANDARDS, STANDARDS, STANDARDS

9:30 - Richard Wright (BBC Archives): Review of Audiovisual Preservation ([video](#), [slides](#))

Place for everyone's notes

- Talking about strategies (transfers, digitisation, making files, etc.) more than standards
- "I'm retired so I can create trouble"- talking to oral history society in 2013: "If you don't have money you get on with it anyway". "This is it, birdseye" (old American cultural reference) - there is no time to wait
- The size of the problem: 2002 paper & survey from around 2002: 1 million hours of film, 1.6 million hours of video recordings, and 2 million hours of audio recordings in ten archives → estimate times 10 as figure for holdings across Europe at that point in time.
- Survey work across time to estimate the size of the problem:
 - 1981 BUFVC (640 audio-visual collections)
 - 2002 Presto (1 mio hrs of film, 1.6 mio hrs of video recordings, 2 mio hrs of audio recordings - ⅔ obsolete, ⅓ damaged, ¼ fragile)
 - 2004 PrestoPrime (20 European countries, 10 million hours)
 - 2007 CAVPP California Preservation Survey of Moving Images (32 libraries, 1 million moving image and sound recordings)
 - 2008 TAPE (374 AV collections across Europe: 25 mio hours - 5 mio hour overlap with PrestoPrime → 30 mio hours documented)
 - 2009 Indiana University - sobering thought: large projects take a decade to come to fruition 560k items on one campus
 - 2015 BL Save our Sounds (1.8 mio recordings, 3000 collections, 488 "collection holders" in UK → most of those not digitized)
 - 2018 BFI Heritage 2022
- No need to do surveys anymore - need to know condition, value, and come up with preservation strategy for the material
- All AV content should be in a formal strategy - doesn't take time or money but thinking and legwork: general strategy for what items are safe and which are at risk
- For inspiration, see Voltaire, Ray Edmondson. What have we been doing so far?

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- 1970 Nitrate won't wait slogan - but it now outlasted acetate, should not have been destroyed
 - Copied analogue video to digital video - not a final solution: anything on a shelf is a problem
 - Copying to file formats was exotic in the 1990s (MPEG-2 at 20 Mbits/s at BBC in the late 1990s) - uncompressed was seen as irresponsible then
 - 2000s ripping & transferring - IASA journal criticized Wright for not applying preservation to originals - what to do with originals is not an engineering problem
 - Digital preservation: economic pressures since 2008 - new budget-friendly digitization methods (FastForward et al.) but not preservation quality
 - Some lower-cost approaches with higher quality results:
 - [RADD](#) \$15 / tape for Wisconsin institutions
 - Iowa state "Building a video preservation rack"
 - XFR Collective pop-up transfer stations
 - DC Public Library Memory Lab
 - BL setting up audio transfer stations in regional libraries across UK
 - Archive quality - Indiana, Tate, MOMA committed to highest quality digitization
 - Question is: "how low can you go"?
 - "No time to wait" versus "You won't get a second chance" approaches for transfer
 - BBC map / matrix with preservation strategy for collection parts
 - Never had a budget for doing re-digitization
 - Preservation map / strategy / plan: no reason not to!
 - Survey: in early 2000s people digitised 1.5% of collections / year
 - Gotten worse since the 2010s
 - Lucky archive vs unlucky archive - will lose ¼ to ½ of pre-2000s analogue archive content
 - Data on tape prediction: storage migration to be replaced with managed storage
 - Equipment lasts longer than predicted but not with video
 - There is a lot more material out there than estimated 18 years ago!
 - Digitization efforts need to be doubled to save half or 2/3s

[Image by Reto Kromer](#)

[Image by Reto Kromer](#)

9:55 - Lars Gaustad: Presenting the initial IASA TC 06 (slides)

- Guidelines presented in two parts - [find them here!](#)
- Equally important: [FADGI guidelines](#)
- Intended audience: technically sophisticated managers
- Broadcast & video tech is complex! Different systems according to geography
- Payload added beyond video & sound: subs, captions, timecode, ... rule-making & standardization varied across the world
- TC-06 authors believe digitisation discussion so far is too limited - not taking payload into account
- Target formats
 - Sometimes sidecar files for subs etc
 - Containers/wrappers
 - Metadata
- Recommended formats: Uncompressed v210 in MXF, Lossless JPEG 2000 in MXF, FFV1 in Matroska

10:20 - Jimi Jones: So Many Standards, So Little Time: Initial Finding and Analysis ([video](#), [continued](#), [slides](#))

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- Qualitative analysis of 2 examples of video digitisation standards development and implementation
 - AS-07
 - MXF/lossless JPEG2000
 - Open Source: MKV/FFV1
 - Digital format evolution through a theoretical lense:
 - Jonathan Sterne
 - Trevor Pinch
 - Steve Woolgar
 - Political economy - promulgation influenced by # resources brought in by actors
 - Study levels of adoption Vincent Moscovice political analysis of communication
 - Carl Cargill's work
 - Ole Hanseth's work on power relations
 - What socio-technical factors influence social informatic questions and decisions
 - What do specs mean to different users? Are there group identities?
 - Is there interpretability of meaning?
 - Research qs
 - How do power dynamics influence
 - What role is there for open source / industry-influenced
 - So far: massive change - no longer hand-me-down tech for archives
 - A lot more DIY solutions
 - Twitter handle: @JJonesArchivist

10:45 - Dave Rice: Status of CELLAR ([video](#) - no audio, [slides](#))

- MediaConch arose from [PREFORMA project](#)
- Presented CELLAR chartered to IETF - now [working group](#) - highly transparent way of working
 - Standardize KV 1 - 3 and create fully standard adhering v4
 - FFV1 version 4 future (version 2 never implemented so out of scope)
 - Similar approach for FLAC
- All standards moved to github <https://github.com/FFmpeg/FFV1>
 - [ffmpeg/ffv1](#)
 - Ebml-specification
 - Matroska-specification

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- Managed in Markdown format - IETS helps convert to formal specification
 - Some [specifications](#) split up - b/c of length
 - Matroska codec document - how to store # encodings
 - Tagging doc
 - Rest of the structure in spec
 - EBML = binary XML format that forms the foundation for Matroska
 - FFV1 v4: working on what else needs to be implemented to make it preservation friendly
 - Bayer encoding
 - FFV1 [issue tracker](#) is becoming smaller - mostly future wishes
 - Matroska still has a large [wish list](#) of things to finish & add

Q&A

Funding needed for implementation? Not sure!

10:55 - Sophie Bunz (chair): How we FFV1 & How we Matroska; Panelists: Joanna White, Carl Eugen Hoyos, Dave Rice ([video](#) - no audio)

- Joanna: carried out encoding tasks with various slice options at Media Archive Central England to consider adoption
- Audience: who uses preservation or intermediate
- SB: Adoption of FFV1 in the room? (10-15 people? Many more people considering it in the future). What other formats are you using?
- Audience: MXF, not with JPEG2000. 10-bit uncompressed.
- How widely is FFV1 in use? Carl: not only in archive world - no real statistics, which is a property of open source project. VLC has stats, we don't. I know ppl use it b/c of #NTTW2. (and Dave). Safe to assume ppl use it as intermediary format to transfer from one format to another. There are bug reports though - so that's a sign.
- What makes FFV1 good? Dave: FFV1 advantages are true for many lossless formats but size is significant - 1/3d smaller than uncompressed. Which makes workflow go faster (rsync, checksum, ...) and creates less e-waste. Also has a lot of self-description whereas uncompressed relies on container. As of v3 there's checksums for each frame and even slices inside of frames so you can see which sectors are impacted. (you can reverse the polynomial division...)

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- Interest seems to be increasing - where are we now / what are milestones for standardization & adoption? **Dave:** FFV1 is assigned for reviews from other IETF working groups - soon after the doc will go into last call mode and to IETF steering group to adopt it. Time frame: deadlines probably whooshed by b/c of a lot of voluntary work. Lot of work done in the group to not break current implementations. (Carl Eugen appreciates it). Instead of forcing the spec, the spec documents prior mistakes in implementations (e.g. 'RBG' instead of 'RGB'). Carl Eugen remembers VP9 specification - where differences were covered saying that implementation was leading.
 - Process at MACE? **Joanna:** MACE is small indy charitable org. Not much time to process all available info - but influenced by previous #NTTW events (and [Mike Casey's white paper](#)) FFV1 seemed like a rock amidst codec confusion. Got ffmpeg on workstation via archive trustee. Joanna's a video producer originally - took steps to research implementation. Turned out much easier to work with than expected. Would be nice to have resource available for archive industry (like [ffmprovisr](#) or the [FFV1 Cheat Sheet](#) or [Reto's commands](#))
 - General slice option if you don't choose? **Dave:** not sure about default - image is cut into pieces encoded separately and brought back together for storage. Uses your computer's resources more efficiently for encoding & decoding.
 - What are other aspects to look at? **Dave:** normally in ffmpeg I use ``-g 1`` which means every frame should be self-contained - otherwise information for one frame would be reduced to the other, which would mean damage's impact would be bigger - **Carl:** normally there's no disadvantage in using ``-g 1`` - does not affect file size (so far). Also like to declare properties to make sure content is as expected - **Carl:** AVI did define an aspect ratio but it's not supported by Windows Media Player.
 - **Joanna:** Slice CRC - as a user how can I experience? How do I get notified? **Dave:** When you decode it will report when it encounters a CRC error and give a timestamp. There's value in knowing the frame - but do I need to know where precisely? Turns out it is useful for error concealment - the decoder will be able to conceal it by copying info over from a prior frame.
 - What would MACE's workflow look like if implemented? **Joanna:** Would like to have capture directly from workstation to FFV1. Usually also need some editing function prior to preservation. Use Shockput as editing and QCTools at the moment. Also interested in developments around RAWcooked. Would be great to have FFV1 captured directly to tape. **Dave:** usetas well as it supports our Blackmagic cards. For editing: struggled with dilemma - wanted to preserve entire tape (for colour bars etc) but also have edited versions for accessibility. Ended up digitizing entire tape and then logging what time content starts & stops. Bash script encoded master file into access copy using that timecode. **Joanna:** now

re-encoding YUY2 and (...) files on directory-based automation. Strength of FFV1 is using 1 - 2 workstations and reaching a good result - using Irish Film Institute [IFI's python codes](#).

Excitement is about size as it results in a massive time gain.

- Peter B: 3 points
 - GOP size
 - G1 influence
 - Capturing directly to FFV1: working on VirtualDub2 fork that does this (Windows only)
- Kieran: How can we make FFmpeg more useful to users like you? MXF (the other side) creating barrier of entry. **Joanna:** How can I deal with DPX into Premiere Pro? Maybe I can transcode to ProRes 4444? Nothing quite works. Creating space where we can communicate with each other?

HORIZON SCANNING

11:25 - Martin Wrigley: Preservation Action Registry ([video](#), [slides](#))

- How do you apply and exchange best practices? [Preservation Action Registry!](#)
- Open Preservation Foundation provides stewardship of open source tools for DigiPres community.
 - OPF Worked on PREFORMA's MediaConch sister project [VeraPDF](#) for standardizing / checking PDF/a
 - Open source Reference Toolset - software and standards, development roadmaps
 - OPF provides tech clinics, workshops, webinars, host services like [COPTR](#) tool registry
- Generic process for reference
 - Policy drives decision making - what do you do after validation
- Realised that video aspect is missing in the toolkit.

- Mechanism needed to exchange best practice between systems that don't talk to each other (Preservica, Archivematica): Preservation Action Registry (PAR)! Funded by JISC to help researchers archive research data. RDSS project.
- Preservica vs Archivematica: PAR ---> Building common language between Preservica & Archivematica systems - formats, preservation actions, ...
- Includes Common framework, JSON schemas, common APIs and interfaces, executable preservation actions & proof of concept is built. This will work.
- To do now:
 - Looking for more use cases
 - Looking for more org to be involved

<http://openpreservation.org>

Q: How many members do you have at the moment?

A: 30-50

Q: Any plans to involve other systems (other than Preservica and Archivematica)?

A: Yes. Please talk to us

Erwin: bitcurator has a list of best practices. Ffmprovisr and ffmpeg cheat sheet.

11:50 Reto Kromer: Beyond RGB: Multispectral imaging and FFV1 ([video](#), [slides](#))

Using FFV1 for something it wasn't designed for

- In the past: film scanners use bayer pattern scanners and RAW storage for data. Current FFV1 version 3 does not. Asked at #NTTW2 if version 4 could use it natively as well. Today need to de-bayer raw data to store them into FFV1 - so first blow up data, then compress data again. Work is going on - implementation either in v3 or v4.
- In the present: RGB not always sufficient for restoration of highly damaged film content. There's a need for multispectral imaging. From flavour of NUT / multiple RGB48 to Matroska/FFV1.3. Hopefully FFV1.4 will have a better solution than the current reto.ch hack. Presented [self-made multispectral film scanner](#) (~20k \$\$ or €€) that works with Diamant restoration software.
- Compression is useful for conservation, not for restoration.
- Future: Hyperspectral imaging. Hyper = A lot of difference bands. Usually 15 bands. Now already 15 bands, so the definition is not quite accurate. It should be more about replace values with functions.
- If you want to find out more: Follow us on Twitter

Q: File size?

A: 5 bands = 5 times the size. Compression algorithm can be optimized to keep the size manageable. I won't be applying it in any case. But if you need it, then the tool is there.

Q (Stephen McConnachie): What's the benefit over normal film scanning?

A: Today it makes sense only for some cases because of the cost. Only few tools able to manage. In the future it might be different. If you don't have enough RGB info in film stock, you can bring out more information. Right now,. If you have completely faded film, you can try to regain the colors by using chemical processes. But it's dangerous. We do not know whether we will destroy the element or not. However, if it's multispectral imaging, we might get more information for the restoration process.

--- LUNCH BREAK ---

13:00 - Peter Bubestinger-Steindl: Open Source & Long Term ([video](#), [slides](#))

- "Just using 'open stuff' won't fix your problems -- it might even make things worse" (Frankfurt presentation)

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- Which applies to anything: can you work with it? Can you maintain it?
 - Popular mistakes are:
 - Underestimating the (environment and starting) conditions
 - Do you value the FLOSS/FOSS freedoms (use, study, share, improve) or are you looking for smt cheap?
 - Resource allocation
 - Who's the community? Someone has to fix issues. "We're just users" mentality.
 - Most frequent reason people want to use FOSS
 - "We need a free alternative"
 - Because .. "We can save the money to buy smt proprietary"
 - Rarely happen but it should happen more: "We want to study/share/improve our digital workflows. Do you know a FOSS solution?"
 - Free as in...
 - Idea that "Free" can't be as good? software 's as good as you want it to be - and will always have bugs
 - Water - when is non-free water better?
 - How can it be professional? (while pro's use it)
 - How many other work with your tools
 - Great GUIs, great support?
 - What if REAL == FREE?
 - Would there be anyone who doesn't want free if it's better than non-free option?
 - "Environmental and starting conditions matter." Using planting tree in the middle of a road as an example to highlight that it is different from a tree in the forest. Forest is a self-sustaining system.

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- Photo credit: <https://twitter.com/criticalsenses/status/1055433250389348352?s=09>
- OSS is infrastructure - [Roads and Bridges](#) report: FOSS underpins much infrastructure without always being properly funded
 - Not all public orgs allowed to fund FOSS development
 - Public money? [Publiccode.eu](#)! => letter writing effort to convince officials
 - Not all projects funded continuously - abandonware / orphan projects - while environment changes
- [Top reasons](#) FOSS dev leave projects [OR why human stop doing things]
 - Lack of interest (new idea, let's hack it, done?, move on)
 - Lack of patience (with impatient users)
 - Lack of resources (time/money)
 - Change of profession
 - Creative differences (human differences)
- Who are using these tools? What if they disappear?
 - Mediainfo

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- VLC
 - Wikipedia
 - Firefox
 - FFmpeg
 - QCTools
 - The crux is “How much do you value it?”
 - “YOU - the user” is the community.
 - [Help a coder, even if you can't code](#)

Q (Martin Wrigley, OPF): OPF picks up on orphan projects - what should #1 be?

A: I will think about it.

EMERGING MEDIA

13:25 - Evanthisa Samaras: Archiving VFX: A research project to preserve evidence of film digital visual effects production (University of Technology, Sydney) ([video](#), [slides](#))

Film VFX

- Industry: combine computer animation fx with live action
- Doesn't always happen at end of filming - can happen before filming starts. To help with visually representing concepts etc.
- ~ 500 companies around the world - bid on possibility to work on **shots** in film projects
- Mostly from Hollywood - Marvel, Disney, etc.
- VFX Archiving -> DOESN'T really exist.
- Industry don't hire record managers
- VFX companies don't own the rights of the work. Generally == work-for-hire
- No consistencies from project to project, even within project
- Archiving Challenges
 - #1 Complex: diverse formats, volumes, media
 - #2 Multiple agents working on one project
 - #3 Obsolescence: destined to disappear

Picture credit: <https://twitter.com/DaleLore/status/1055440118545371136>

- Case study: the lost picture show [paper](#) by Marty Perlmutter
- Seagrass number generator - had to be recreated frame by frame not even 10 years after the film's release

About the research

- Research driven out of a VFX school called the UTS Animal Logic Academy - presently school has 3 PhD candidates
- Trying to convince VFX industry to apply archival practices
- Why archive VFX?
 - Provenance (how, why and who)
 - Knowledge base for current and future VFX productions and process
 - Historical and cultural insights into filmmaking, visual storytelling, technical production and digital design practices

animallogicacademy.uts.edu.au

Q&A

Q: BFI have similar issues. Cost to embrace this kind of work?

A: A lot of studios have under the table agreement with these companies. Industry have to carry themselves. Hard to project how much it'll cost. Industry have sophisticated infrastructure, so it's technically possible to do it. But Evanthia wants to talk to collecting institutions whether keen to take it in. Companies shouldn't be expected to archive these themselves.

Twitter handle: @CyberKittyFace

13:35 - Jack McConchie, Tom Ensom: Developing a High Level Preservation Strategy for Virtual Reality Artworks ([video](#), [slides](#))

- Project supported by Lumen Foundation
- Move from exploratory research to strategy for acquisition & preservation
- Focus on 360 video (pre-rendered frames) + real-time 3D (dynamically generated and interactive)

Introduction

- Moving from exploratory research to strategy for acquisition and preservation
- First stages of project have explored:
 - The core components of VR systems (software and hardware) and their relationships
 - Production and playback of 360 video VR works
 - Production and playback of real-time 3D VR works
 - Initial exploration of preservation strategies for both the above

PASSIVE EXPERIENCE | **360 Video** | **Real-Time 3D** | **INTERACTIVE EXPERIENCE**

MediaArea Live Stream

- Happily ignoring AR so far
- Hardware involved
- Software applications
 - Runtime: work underway to standardize

- 360 video
 - Monoscopic video captured with dual fisheye lenses (no depth information)
 - Stereoscopic 3D has multiple lenses, creating depth for the eyes with overlapping imagery
 - High frame rate needed (60 fps) to prevent nausea
 - Players use combo of mesh and 3D-map to display equirectangular forms
 - like world maps, the image has pixel distortion
 - Also straight lines shown as curves which influences possible compression
 - Cubemap compression: 25% smaller for similar quality
 - Equiangular cubemap
 - Pyramid style projection developed by facebook
 - Consequence of these shapes has consequence that shape of 3d and projection map need to be stored alongside it. Google media group provides mathematical method to store it - not yet fully adopted.
 - Peculiar file naming - string of characters inserted into filename
 - Ambisonic audio
 - First-order ambisonics "a-format" has 4 channels
 - Converted into B format - also 4 channels - needs virtual head to be put in its sphere to make sense (head-related tracking information) with calculations

being done in real time by the player, depending on where your head is in space

- Channels can be ordered in various ways
- Real-time 3D involves rendering of frames on the fly
 - glTF succeeds Collada as an open spec file format for 3D assets - not yet widely adopted
 - What's a 3D model? Objects that fill virtual space - combo of mesh (the structure) and 3D maps (how structures are projected onto it) + animation data
 - Blender, ZBrush, MAYA - proprietary and open tools
 - 3D modelling for material (texture maps and shader) - GIMP, Photoshop, Substance Painter - layering of texture maps in uncompressed images
 - 3D assets brought together in an engine: Unreal, Unity, Source2, CryEngine and with a particular VR runtime. Both Unity and Unreal have open repositories but with very restrictive licensing.
 - Engine packages the whole as software for playback
 - Playback software usually built for particular machine type
 - VR Runtimes eg steamvr, oculus runtime, openxr, WebVR
 - Graphics API directx, metal, opengl, Vulkan (open standard succeeding OpenGL)
 - Graphics Processing Unit to carry out the graphics processing - linked to specific drivers e.g. Vulkan (succeeding OpenGL)
 - Lenses require specific type of distortion
 - Timewarps & spacewarps all handled by VR runtime
 - Not Losing this info is important for preservation

Exploring Preservation Strategies

- [Insert picture of slide here][working on it]

Next Steps: Exploring Preservation Strategies

	General	360 Video	Real-Time 3D
Migration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Headset lens distortion algorithms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moving between projection types • Variability in players 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How reliable are the open 3D asset standards • Re-creating a 3D scene in different engines
Emulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emulating VR runtimes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emulating 360 video players 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Paravirtualization and passthrough for real-time 3D VR
Documentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Field of view video capture • Accounts of experience 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Documenting projection type 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 360 video capture

Q&A

- Q: Cinema now working on 4K, 8K - can you imagine what resolutions we will be looking at to get a 4K-equivalent image as per cinema?

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- A: Cannot predict because a lot of dependencies.
 - Q: What are your thoughts regarding hardware preservation (controllers, headsets, ...)?
 - A: trying to understand what characteristics hardware bring to the experience
 - Experience of Oculus TK1 - lots of pixelation - is that significant? Depends on artist / the work
 - Looking at hardware-independent strategies

14:50 - Stephen McConnachie (chair): Emerging Media: collecting, preservation and access challenges. Panelists: Erwin Verbruggen, Judy Wilcocks, Caylin Smith, Patricia Falcao ([video](#), [slides](#))

Introduction by SM

UK gov completing investment profile into immersive storytelling, immersive innovation. Industry speculate huge growth area, gov is funding.

Case Study Interactive Documentary by EV

- Intro of @benglabs.
- Trying to create an interactive documentary canon. How do we preserve these idfa DOCLAB.
- We speak a new and powerful language capable of saying things no other language can say, but few have realized this, and even fewer have found what to say. Jonathan Harris.
- DOCLAB annual event. Physical exhibit. Industry event. Preservation perspective - interesting. Bring browser experience to live audiences. Like a performance of these pieces.
- Inspired by Dutch Game Canon -> DOCLAB turned 10. What are the seminal works? Aren't we doing something about the preservation of these?
- DOCLAB likes to keep it undefined. Some type of [xyz???], interaction, digital technology, captured reality
- A lot of industry interest.
- The remit of @benglabs, pick up works that fall under our collection, Dutch producers, creators.
- DOCLAB ⇒ Immersive network. @benglabs going back and forth with them. Out of these meetings, something Canada supports WebRecorder development.
- Case Studies
 - Using VR to showcasing art.
 - I'm Not Home Video - Bert Hana

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- One person film every corner of vacation house. Create VR.
 - Bear 71 VR
 - Rely a lot on Adobe Flash. Costly. Expensive. Not impossible. @benglabs work to transfer to VR.
 - Clklikckkick.click
 - Story based on what your mouse is doing
 - Refugee Republic
 - [INSERT Screenshots] what webrecorder will get when you try to capture.

Publications.beeldengeluid.nl

- => Preserving IInteractives
- => Server-Side web archiving
- => Preserving the Emerging

Case study Interactive narrative by CS

Intro

Breathe - A Ghost Story by Kate Pullinger

Context

UK Non-Print Legal deposit. The Legal Deposit Libraries (Non-Print Works) Regulations 2013. Allow libraries to collection publications in digital formats.

Emerging format project

April 2017 - present (two year project). Identifying publication that are in scope to collect under legal deposit. Focused on 3 types of content: ebook, web-based interactive narrative, structured data (e.g. stats, official reports)

About Breathe

Written for the web. Optimised for mobile. It tries to personalised narrative to the reader's surroundings - use of camera, GPS and weather data.

- Mainly textual. White background, black text.
- Different types of interactions e.g. tilting the screen to reveal the full story
- Behavior of the work affected by device i.e. OS, browser

Capturing Breath using web archiving tools

- Heritrix
 - Crawling engine to capture web archive. We know there are problems capturing dynamic content. We tried it anyway.
 - Demo of what Heritrix managed to get → WHITE NOTHING
- Webrecorder
 - By RHIZOME.
 - Demo of what webrecorder managed to get → Not much. Broken image. Quite a bit of 404 errors.

Next Steps

- Engage with Editions at Play to better understand
- Engage with Webrecorder community

Twitter handle: @caylinssmith

Panel Discussion

- SM: Judy you have tough experience material store or save.
- JW: Collection ambition outstrip tech capabilities. Up to two years ago, could deal with what we were collecting . Aware of limitations. Only 2 full time staff (keen amateurs). Recently it's gotten so complicated, we do not know what to do. Example: Collection VR, we have raw files and executable etc. We have an artwork but we can't look at it.
- SM: Tate will collect?
- PF: VR → 10 work last 10 years. Last year we had three. 30 days just to analyse the work.
- SM: We are decades away from standards for moving images. What can we learn, what we've done before? Is this completely new ground
- EV: Richard started the day with analogue materials. With DOCLAB, we look at similarities with other canon. There's someone out there who knows to do this. Preserving is not one time fix, it's continual process.
- SM: Have we talked to the makers/creators regarding preserving these?
- CS: We have to reach out to the creators to know more about how it's built. Need more meetings. Complete shift in thinking to preserve and make it accessible.
- SM: Talking to creators is the process when you archive/preserve complicated mixed-media artwork right?

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- PF: Yes.
 - SM: Standards? Is it too soon for us to tell the industry standardise?
 - EV: Hype cycle of technology. Not common household yet, but we're getting there. We, as archivist, can sit back and let the industry figure it out. But in a way, that's why we're all here at #nttw3, we are trying to be more involved.
 - SM: Maybe there's a scope for us to be more involved in the industry.
 - Q (Martin, OPF): VR is the most simple. Breathe is AR. How do you capture the context?
 - SM: Scale of challenges for broad and deep.
 - EV: Lessons learned: Approaching media as performance. Record how it was like. How people engage with it. Record reactions. At least we have that if everything disappears.
 - Q (David): Maybe something is better than nothing. YouTube → kids watch kids playing games. Good example of if you don't have the software, you have the documentation, how it was used. Recording that is a type of preservation.
 - SM: Do something is better → Comparable to video tape. If you don't act quickly, you assume you have time.
 - CS: Emerging format project. In scope. Record someone going through a work. Put together with the component files, until technology or know-how to recreate it.
 - Q (Somaya): How much you wish you're a creator/producer? Will you understand the challenges better?
 - SM: UK TV moved to file-based. Very successful in production and archival. Emerging vs lockdown.
 - JW: I work in an Art school. It's very hard to lock down artists.

15:35 - Ernesto Coto and Andrew Brown: Automated Tagging of Image and Video Collections using Face Recognition (Oxford Uni Visual Geometry Group) ([video](#), [slides](#))

- Untagged BFI dataset
- Untagged BBC dataset

Facial recognition in unconstrained condition very challenging: different ages, different facial hair, different emotions, different angles

1. Detect faces & crop them
2. Create feature vector (list of numbers)

-
3. Match it with known identities
 4. Label which is the closest

Matching is easy but only works if it features the identity, not age, pose and light. Convolutional Neural Network with 13+ parameters creates a feature vector that just represents identity. Needs to be trained - by using labeled VGGFace2 dataset (3M images, 300 images for each 9000s identities).

BFI Browser

BFI gave names of 11000 ppl of interest & 46000 images. Done in 3 stages:

1. Download selection of images from image search engine
2. Extract feature vector for each
3. Detect images in the 46000 provided images - if above threshold then labeled as such

Easy to download images for very famous people. Using clustering with Google images famous people are identified (~6,500). Results returned in a grid ranked by best ranking.

BFI Browser: zeus.robots.ox.ac.uk/bfi_browser (login required). Limit search to actors that are credited as present in a film to improve results. 3 types of anomalies in metadata:

1. Labeled as wrong film
2. Images labeled with wrong film but actors not in credits
3. Surprise appearance (background images)

System automatically indicates whether error is in metadata or in detection.

BBC News Search

5 million images 2007 - 2012. APplied

http://zeus.robots.ox.ac.uk/bbc_search

- No pre-tagged images in the dataset, tagging is done on the fly
- Uses query to download google image results and compare features to all faces in the dataset
- Programs repeat as people come up continually in a program
- Can select second face and give results
- Can also pre-generate - planning to extend the system to include compound queries (more than one thing)

-
- Integrate searching for multiple people

More funny stuff to play with at robots.ox.ac.uk/~vgg/

Q&A

- False positives?
- Will BFI's 46K image collection be made available to experiment? No but BFI is happy to collaborate on R&D. Contact Stephen McConnachie: @mcnatch / stephen.mcconnachie@bfi.org.uk
- Engine is FOSS? People search released this year under open source version - find it on the Oxford page: robots.ox.ac.uk/~vgg/
- Absolute tags are used only under very high positive ranking
- David Walsh: What's time & effort here? 2 minutes or 2 months processing? BFI project was an entire Master's project. Also, depends on hardware.

16:00 - Kieran Kunhya: Supporting niche formats and niche hardware in open source software and operating systems ([video](#), [slides](#))

- Speaking in personal capacity, even though my organisation is sponsoring NTTW3
- Who am I? Open source multimedia mostly working on FFmpeg and x264
- FFmpeg
 - Multimedia processing library. Many Web browsers implement complex specs and the web is super complex these days. Nothing super comparable to FFmpeg - span is vast. Basis for many other applications - VLC, browsers, smart TV
 - Written in C - not fashionable but widely supported & works on weird devices
 - Not locked down by particular vendor ('market segmentation')
- Reverse engineering
 - Giants in the field
- It's difficult to get into multimedia programming now as so much has been done already
 - Modern high-performance formats like AV1 can't be understood by any one person
 - Supporting niche formats helps staying familiar with concepts e.g. entropy coding, DCT.
- Niche format example: MPEG-4 Sstp ticket
 - For indie developers: very expensive to buy common specifications
 - Can be found on some Chinese websites with some effort

-
- Most codecs involve *entropy coding* which either works or it doesn't
 - Higher quality transforms needed higher float IDCT
 - No reference decoder so picture needed tweaking until it looked ok
 - A lot of (Christmas/ Easter) work to template integers
 - Crazy DPCM blocks
 - GoPro Press release "core technology" bits of the codec were used
 - Cineform - SMPTE VC-5 specification
 - Could have reverse-engineered but luckily codebook was available
 - Got HD working in 2002 - really simple, really fast
 - Opensourced the format thanks to Kieran's work!
 - <https://medium.com/@kierank/reverse-engineering-the-gopro-cineform-codec-7411312bfe1c>
 - Physical media files
 - Panasonic P2 - PCI-based
 - Sony SxS cards PCI-express based (~modern phone storage)
 - Now commodity - 10/15 yrs ago high-end, all closed source drivers - won't work in a 100 years
 - Linux driver will work - which is a way of preserving hardware features
 - Panasonic P2
 - Modern PCI-express is backward compatible with legacy PCI (b/c of military?)
 - Cameras run on linux - can ask for source code to read these cards
 - Found linux 2.4 driver (2001)
 - github.com/kierank/p2card
 - Sony SxS
 - No driver found
 - Needed CPU with IOMMU - found machine with correct memory mapping
 - Memory cards are block-based devices
 - Use dd to read block by block
 - No working DMA (Direct Memory Access) yet so very slow
 - github.com/kierank/sxs-linux - allows reading, writing would be next step

Reverse engineering coming to completion?

- Codecs are reverse-engineered faster than they're being created!
 - (born-compressed) materials will be playable much longer than initially expected
- Still there are many proprietary formats out there

-
- Some readers hardware-based
 - Important to use commodity hardware

Q&A

- Ever had difficult questions about the work you're doing (people not very happy with what you do → knock on your door)?
 - Only from community - GoPro's response was positively surprising!
- Digital Cinema / IMF codecs perfectly playable but packaged - could FFmpeg ever do that?
 - There are ppl who want that, but think it should be done at higher layer - interpretation of the package needs something to understand the sum of the parts

16:25 Derek Buitenhuis: Every Solution is Wrong: Normalizing Ambiguous, Broken, and Pants-on-Head Crazy Media (Vimeo, VideoLAN, Twitter troll) ([video](#), [slides](#))

- World's going file-based - not all nice - you'll need to deal with crap
- Not everyone has luxury of being able to require ingested materials to follow guidelines
 - Need to ingest wide array of media
 - Need to provide easy, good feedback to improve
- NOT for purists: munge a lot of stuff! [No-nos in the archival world]
- Before doing anything pick which stream to use
 - For video: make a score to be likely to work
 - For audio: prefer downmixed version, prefer streams with earlier start times
- Indexing is first thing what happens when receiving a file (not decoding)
 - Shove index somewhere
- Chunk transcoding
 - Key frames are not scene changes
- Scaling: doesn't matter what you do - ppl will hate you
 - Resized to mod 2
- Resampling: depends on compression level
- [I'm sorry this is too fast and too technical for me to follow - but good stuff :)]
 - Slides have all the text!
- Subs: ppl pasting subtitles in word files and uploading them <:)
- Stuff that was once cool
 - Apple slo-mo - if created by iPhone version x and framerate is x, then...

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- ISOBMFF

Q&A

- How do you identify when something's bad?
 - Vimeo support forwards things!
- Some ppl use Vimeo as archive - do you keep the original?
 - Users have option to keep original file (and option to create AVC intra mezzanine even)
- Out of sync file era - why?
 - Often ffmpeg c-cly timestamp code is old and needs an update (noone wants to touch the poo)
- Favourite file format?
 - Pseudo file format encoded instructions on how to animate a fire, which old quicktime would do - QuickTime had that built in for 10 years although only 1 file existed
- How to make your life easier? Large set of guidelines on Vimeo
<https://vimeo.com/help/compression>
- You do delete files?
 - We used to - which we still keep complaints about
 - It's a business aspect - not tech / some ppl pay for keeping, others didn't check a box

16:50 Ben Cartwright-Cox: Archiving DAB/DAB+ Feeds ([video](#), [slides](#))

- Just a rogue archiver
- All good things start with a good wikipedia binge: lost television broadcast page
 - BBC redux helps some of that
 - But lost some so doesn't trust them
- How about getting DAB sticks and dumping to disk?
- Got a telco rack then built a server rack instead
 - Intention to hold 500GB of content and delete stuff
- Current setup is now NAS for backup + HP microserver
 - Bit expensive
- Fed through adhesive aerials

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- Some friends do this - in NL, in US (not really DAB as US did digital radio wrong), in Australia (no pic)
 - BBC all use Mpeg-2 (all sounds crap), Triple j uses AAC,
 - Critical paths
 - Recording - airwaves don't repeat themselves, with Bstreamer & 156 lines of code
 - Homemade decoders for DAB+ and the US FM/DAB hybrid, buffered by RAM for possible power outage
 - Tagging - "btagger" thanks to EPG decoding and Dynamic label decoding (reverse-engineered) & now playing info on various websites - APIs still online luckily + save original JSON payload files just in case
 - Playback: low priority - breaks a lot
 - "BDUX adio Recall System" - retro aesthetic
 - Data isn't always great
 - Simulcasts are annoying
 - Misspellings
 - Embargoes left in API
 - Lessons learned
 - NTP syncing

Q&A

- Do you have an objective quality metric?
 - b/c encoder is terrible
- [Kaleidoscope] Great to see people getting solutions to things being lost!
 - Still looking for mirror - come talk to us
- Have you tried archiving DRM? Thoughts on storing all satellite?
 - Would love to do this! Tried with pirate radio to find roof space - don't have physical space or disk space

Friday, October 26th

9:15 - Dave Rice: No Time to Wait Introduction ([video](#), [slides](#))

Conference cost €5,500 out of a €6000 conference budget, thanks to sponsorships and host BFI.

A host organisation for #nttw4 is very welcome!

9:20 - Yvonne Ng (Senior Archivist, WITNESS): Accessible workflows for collecting and preserving video evidence for human rights ([video](#), [slides](#))

- WITNESS: org uses video to expose human rights abuse
- Context for tech discussions & impact of preserving AV materials outside of archives
- Examples of video as evidence
- DRC Military tribunal, Sep 2018 - first time video used as evidence in Congolese trial
 - a. Atmosphere changed after showing video, b/c showed brutality and impact
 - b. Eyewitnessproject.org - specialized app to capture important device metadata, create closed chain of custody
- Walter Scott case, 2015 - shot in the back by police officer, filmed by bystander on phone
 - a. Became key piece of evidence
- War crimes arrest warrant - increasingly common to use video found on social media
 - a. ICC arrest warrant for "social media executioner" based solely on 7 videos shared on social media
 - b. 1 video originally taken down - only used b/c someone else saved it
 - c. Bellingcat provided research to geolocate, track down, corroborate evidence - <https://www.bellingcat.com/news/mena/2017/09/04/geolocating-libyas-social-media-executioner/>

Collaborations

- Community documentation of police brutality with *El Grito de Sunset Park*
 - a. Street harassment by police, Brooklyn - filmed by bystanders, charges dropped and officer suspended
 - b. Help community documentation like this to demand accountability - necessary b/c many states limit availability of police records
 - c. Helped archive their collection: capture DVs, describe following basic cataloging scheme
 - d. Volunteer-run org with many other priorities (e.g. Hurricane Maria benefit) - needed basic tools & training, uncomplicated workflows, fun & rewarding to operate

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- e. Used both proprietary + FOSS resources & tools
 - f. Elgrito.witness.org planning workbook
 - g. Pre-ingest, ingest (exactly benefit not always clear to users)
 - h. Organic scheme for describing, messy then further developed with Berkeley cop watch, sued ERD for modeling, then implemented in Filemaker
 - i. Used video for creating timelines, background and analysis for video collection + step by step documentation as toolkit
 - Berkeley cop watch (started 1990) project ongoing
 - a. Been around for 25 years, have office but 1 computer only, cameras & volunteers - footage not always offloaded and organised after shifts end. Many records & filemaker in a not very structured way
 - b. Project involved clarifying video collection policy, redesigning database, streamlining video ingest workflows
 - c. Working on workflow documentation in Dropbox Paper (so much better than gdocs)
 - d. Filemaker for videos & follow-up actions - proprietary db
 - Pro: not that expensive, were already using it, nothing else like it - easy to use & massive user base
 - Limitations: installation was out of date, server version very expensive, data isn't stuck but all the work (layout etc) is

Rohingya Genocide Archive

- Find collect social media that documents crimes against humanity
- Partner is Rohingya-led initiative - local person hired as archivist while WITNESS provides training & workflow setup
- In Burma: Facebook ("Hatebook") stand-in for the internet - dozens of whatsapp groups & twitter - lots of first-hand accounts shared on all these channels
- Needed replicable processes that non-technical people could do
- Used youtube-dl (<https://youtube-dl.org/>) for downloading incl metadata - command line so a bit intimidating for some
- Gather additional metadata using the web-based interfaces for Facebook & YouTube APIs - useful as simple GUI for creating queries with curl commands
- Twitter doesn't offer this but offers twurl for twitter api to get json data
- WhatsApp frustrating - no public api, can only access media not metadata

- Not a problem with iphones but androids can only do gmail - so need to download on desktop
- All packages use exactly
- Cataloging in google sheet - emphasis on source, when & where was filmed

Tools exist but are not all easy to use, not always open source

- GUI is cherry on top
- Open source alternative (to eg filemaker) would be nice but proprietary works for now
- Whatsapp is complex to save
- Easy data modeling needed - metadata about video and incidents relating to it
- Identifying duplicate content across platforms

9:45 - Jérôme Martinez: RAWcooked ([video](#), [slides](#))

- Film scans often use raw files - each frame can be 100MB leading to several TB per hour
- Many DPX formats flavors, loose images not playable by e.g. VLC
- Propose FFV1 compression without losing video content
 - No patent risk like there is with e.g. JPEG2000
 - Checksums on slice level
- Tests done for VIAA compared to JPEG2000 lossless different results - average speed is faster with FFV1, but depends on content
- Many people store silence in LPCM - why not compress it? Using FLAC in test
 - Package turns out 1.5 - 3 smaller than DPX/TIFF
 - Natively playable by VLC and all FFmpeg-based players

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- RAWcooked easy command line (instead of intimidating ffmpeg commands) for compress and decompress
 - It is like ZIP, but with a much more efficient compression algorithm and immediately playable by many players
 - Thank you sponsors! (reto.ch and others) - first stable release as of 2 days ago!
 - RAWcooked most compelling reason - cost divided by 2 and speed multiplied by 2.
 - Tool made for archivists - can use more sponsors - good, easy to use tool could benefit from more speed support, GUI, other input formats. Not just for money but for testing & advocacy & documentation. Help out!

Come to the QC Workshop at CNA, Luxembourg, Nov 29, which will focus on QCTools, MediaInfo, MediaConch, RAWcooked! <https://mediaarea.net/QCWorkshop2018>

Q: Source code available?

A: All on github

Q: Is DPX to Matroska mapping publically available?

A: Currently working on that. [RK - All is already on GitHub. Yet documentation readable by non-techies is in preparation.]

**10:10 - Ben Turkus, Kelly Haydon: If we could turn back ...
timecode ([video](#), [slides](#))**

- Granular topic, but a lot of ground to cover! #timecodeadventures
- What is timecode
 - Cher & timecode have been around forever, their relevance is eternally questioned
 - Michael Angeletti (Stanford) case studies - capturing TC is a “huge pain in the ass” with available tools
 - Not the most important part of analog signal - but can be useful to researchers
 - Preservation standards for TC seem underdeveloped
- Problems
 - AS-07 working on integrating more analog signal (multiple TC streams) than other containers (eg MXF) but tools not there to capture it in the stream
 - Software creates bogus TC instead of capturing
 - Not much documentation - some shuffled together from old video magazines from the '80s
- SMPTE timecode is frame numbering system (see B&H Professional Video Handbook) - frame number can travel with content, helps keep signal components in sync during transformations - not equivalent to trash fire timestamp
 - TC we know today standardized by SMPTE/EBU in 1969

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- Now an integral part of production workflows (used for EDLs) - logs have high research value
 - Also part of film production workflows
 - Production workflows usually logged tape numbers in TC
 - Characteristics
 - VITC or LTC -
 - LTC is earlier, often recorded on audio track 2, can't be read at fast speeds, sounds like static
 - VITC is integrated in tape's video track, provides indexing resolution (can be read at all speeds) and frees up 2nd audio channel
 - Drop frame or not
 - Distinguished by colon (non-drop) or semicolon (drop)
 - Continuous or discontinuous
 - Unbroken clocking vs abruptly stopped & started recording (video art, home movies, indie media, etc)
 - TC can help rebuild productions using EDL - can identify, contextualize
 - Production documentation often notes interesting material by their TC,
 - Limitations & recent advances
 - Ben Turkus - brilliant & delightful
 - "Do you really care about TC?" Need to approach it while being aware that we have limited time
 - Problem of TC has not been solved in comprehensive way - or if they have equity was not in mind - high barrier to entry
 - Want to make it possible to capture full TC with regular materials
 - IASA TC-06 great new reference, AS-07 great standard, but need practical advice.
 - Information out there is abstract
 - Carl Fleischhauer 2014 AMIA-L message
 - Problem is two-sided: transmitting through digitization workflow & how to store it in digital file
 - Vrecord & FFmpeg advances
 - Create new structure to store arbitrary data at frame level in FFV1?
 - NYPL transitioned from QT to FFV1 for in-house digitisation with Blackmagic Decklink cards, sponsored vrecord for its development to make it work
 - BMDtools & Vrecord solved decklink issue
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- Could sponsor development instead of problem solving
 - Now in FFmpeg/vrecord: first correct timecode stamp can be stored and sidecar txts can be created
 - Cher test tape showed all the problems inherent
 - Can often trust deck to know what is going on with TC
 - 1 deck card combo allowed capturing LTC, other combo allowed capturing VITC
 - vrecord community welcomes testers
 - Ticked David Crosthwait boxes: discontinuous TC
 - QCTools “learned me more about video than any book”
 - Software like QCTools allows gaining insights, working backwards on issue

Q&A

- Possible to look at developer tools later on, extract now?
 - Is what we try to do
- Can you use vrecord graphically?
 - Depends on video card
- Is there an open source SMPTE LCE decoder?
 - Saw one on Github
 - One more tool mentioned in IASA-TC 6 - (LTCAux?)
- Can you create sampler for FFmpeg?
 - Yes!

10:35 - Jonas Svatos: Building digital audio-visual pipelines using standards IT tools ([video](#), [slides](#))

- Small institutions have manually developed and documented workflows
- Complex workflows with lots of scripting chained together. Hard if you want to do logging. Even harder if you want to audit the logs.
- Manual == deterministic (human errors)
- Hence, archivist should let machines do the heavy lifting. Focus instead on ways to do it better, write better code
- Use automation / orchestration systems
 - Jenkins, Ansible, Rundeck, Buildbot, ...
 - Allow reusing scripts (like [Kieran's!](#))
 - NFA uses Jenkins to great success (also with non-techies thanks to GUI)

- Continuous integration (CI) system

Demo of automation tool developed by NAA(?) using Jenkins

- Job parameters can be defined in the job or through integration via API
- Jenkins can do job chaining - one script after another automatically

Agent-based system - every server in a farm is connected to a master - parameters can trigger only on specific node

- Can also use it as cron commander (for daily tasks)
- Config can be pushed into git repo for versioning. Also can be used to backup workflow elsewhere
- Conclusion: Jenkins is great!

10:45 - Merle Friedrich: Monitoring the risk of file format obsolescence in TIBs AV holdings ([video](#), [slides](#))

Obsolescence

- Ryan 2014 when information is no longer accessible with current technology - becoming rather than being - need to act before information is inaccessible
- Obsolete formats are at risk to become inaccessible by designated community (DC)
- Plenty of formats at TIB (see table, not including long tail formats with < 20 items), all lossy

Amount	Container	Video_Coerce	Audio_Coerce
7384	MPEG-4	AVC	AAC, Version 4
1062	WebM, Format : WebM	VP8	Vorbis
963	MPEG-PS	MPEG Video, Version 2	MPEG Audio, Version 1
765	MPEG-4	AVC	AAC
706	MPEG-PS	MPEG Video, Version 1	MPEG Audio, Version 1
557	MPEG-4	MPEG-4 Visual	AAC, Version 4
421	MPEG-4	MPEG-4 Visual	
210	WebM, Version 2	VP8	Vorbis
175	MPEG-TS	AVC	AC-3
97	MPEG-PS	MPEG Video, Version 2	
93	AVI	AVC	PCM
46	MPEG-PS	MPEG Video, Version 2	AC-3, Format : DVD-Video
44	Flash Video	VP6	MPEG Audio, Version 1
37	MPEG-PS	MPEG Video, Version 2	MPEG Audio, Version 1, Format : MPEG Audio, Version 1, Format : RLE
33	Flash Video	VP6	MPEG Audio, Version 2
31	MPEG-4	AVC	
22	MPEG-PS	MPEG Video, Version 2	MPEG Audio, Version 1, Format : DVD-Video
30	MPEG-4	MPEG-4 Visual	AAC

Normalization

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- Makes preservation planning easier, need less tools but need to migrate - can lead to undocumented changes of material and need more storage if you want to keep the original.
 - TIB formats to FFV1: 10 - 20 x more storage space needed

OAIS

- How do you monitor the risk?

Monitor

- Ryan (2014) file formats like species - 21 indicators for identifying obsolescence, depending on rendering software availability. Conclusion is that available rendering software is the most important one.
- KB NL approach: concept view paths ([Steenbakkers 2015 Digital archiving in the twenty-first century](#)) - need 2 valid view paths for each format

Migration

- Plenty of criteria (Malcolm Todd 2009 tech watch report)
- Test preservation planning with Rosetta - extract tech metadata
- Aim to develop migration plugin for Rosetta to migrate to FFV1/Matroska with FFmpeg

Q&A

- What if you look at transcoding path instead of viewing path?
 - Sounds reasonable
- Love having risk profile - how about linked data repository?
 - See [wikidata for preservation](#) project
- Do we still need to monitor if ffmpeg does it all?
 - Carl Eugen Hoyos: Better be safe than sorry

11:10 - Steve Daly (head of tech BBC archives): BBC Audio and Video Preservation - Using open source tools and ensuring long-term readability ([video](#), [slides](#))

- 10s of PB of digital content but primarily analogue materials
- Digitizing for a long time now ~ 20 yrs, 400,000 video tapes, entire BBC Wales archive (IP2022 stuff) - lean process engineering factory techniques, industry quality assurance

- In-house open source development for a decade

Filenames

- Used to be assetname .mxf
- Now embed md5 checksum of the asset in the filename *assetname_checksum.mxf* makes it more unique & can validate integrity throughout workflow - self-describing and self-validating

Modularity

- Moved to 8 channel building block (modular) pods for ingest incl transcoding etc off to cheap storage array - scalable setup with one computer

SOX: FFT

- Homemade qc player

Barcodes

- Printed half a million for Wales project
- Used for user interface - homemade software recognises action codes e.g. Delete, Stop

Physical scanning

- Include boxes labels etc
- First with flatbed scanners - now with high quality video

VTR Head Errors

- Channel condition: machine 'knows' how well it's capturing
- RSS422 extension to P2 protocol gives you that info on the back as well
- Is stored and presented on timeline to qc operators
- Also capture all the TC - Qc operators to indicate whether discontinuities are expected

File trimming

- Now capture entire tape until end of tape flag
- Scanned paperwork can save going back to original asset
- Nothingness at end of tape sliced off as part of trans-wrap by means of ffmpeg filter black, grey, silence - Cost saving for storage

Longterm

- Creating 10s of 1000s of data tapes - all documentation written to every data tape: includes project description, format description, tech specs of file formats, esp. More esoteric ones, white papers (2013 T. Heritage MXF file), source code, data manifest of entire project, videos describing end-to-end workflows - trying to create plaque next to space craft

mic drop

Q&A

- Who else captures error codes?
 - 50% of commercial products record it, but no post-production tools do
 - Create txt file with error status of every frame that is processed downstream
 - Not good on analog formats but absolute confidence indicator for digital formats
- Charles Fairall: Playing tapes to the end is fantastic but a lot of tapes have a phenomenal amount of blank tape - are we confident we might get to the end of our projects without wearing the heads out?

-
- Is a concern but biggest QC clog used to be checking whether content was fully captured - from a pure factory pov the effort is worth it
 - Different conversation with external suppliers - in-house one person runs 16 machines
 - Stephen McConnachie: what video file formats?
 - Have used archive-specific formats, pleased with benefits but challenges of readability after changes in staffing, funding, ...
 - Great effort of migrating - prefer formats usable in millions of production formats - chose QT uncompressed v210 10 Bit

11:20 - Ashley Blewer (chair): The Developer-Archivist: a Definition of the Profession
Panel: Ashley Blewer, Stephen McConnachie, Kieran O'Leary, Edward Anderson ([video](#))

- Conservation as specific component of museum: conservator-restorer, similar to developer-archivist combines 2 broad fields

How did you come to be Developer-Archivist?

- Stephen: I'm a manager - benefits of having that skillset in your archive
- Kieran: came out of necessity - wanted to implement FFV1 ([see 1st NTTW YouTube for full story](#)) after finding Dave Rice's bash script make lossless
 - Metrics for finding successful
 - Learned python to make it all work cross-platform
 - Manager of things :P
- Ed: joined bfi as curator non-fiction department - ran into catalog issues - enthusiastic about DH distance reading
 - Chuck all titles into dbpedia spotlighting for name entity recognition package, transform into KML geocoding for google maps - which became britain on film project, it's online.
 - Baby names (since 1996)! Application for film - to uncover inherent inadequacies of representation in film
 - Shipped content with code, now focuses on code
- Ashley: archives 1st dev second - worked in film archive focused on learning developing

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- NYPL developer - archiving skills less welcome? Interesting projects in the library context
 - MediaArea projects MediaConch & QCTools (I don't write C++ but made the website, for example, made AVAA)
 - Now at Artefactual with Ross Spencer - being both dev and archivist able to do both
 - Stephen: opportunism - Ed's activities tweaked my antenna so I was opportunistic - couldn't have put out a hiring call but could show the value of writing code by adopting his skills
 - Kieran concurs ^
 - Kieran: Split actual work from designing the workflow. Circular thing.
 - Ashley: tech understanding is underrepresented in archival studies. Think of it certain way to get it done.
 - Stephen: multi-domain / multi-linguality: need to understand technical language but also translating its use to curators.
 - Ashley: think of myself as translator Human-Computer translator.
 - Ed: think of myself as terrible hacker standing on shoulder of giants & superbrains
 - Stephen: Thank you FFmpeg!
 - Ashley: So much work has gone into it that we're building on it
 - Ashley: Working for clients vs working as a loner in non-tech org
 - Kieran: q what happens when a specific skill set leaves? Initially all needed to learn python - but it takes time. Make mistake, go to stackoverflow x 1.000.000
 - Not all need to learn - code
 - Many deadlines little spare time - archivist-developers out there could be hired
 - Non-coders have the vision of where the archives to move to.
 - Ashley commends Kieran for good documentation. Kieran said he referenced it from Dinah Handel.
 - Stephen: Mitigation: need documentation (readthedocs, see dinah handel's bash script docs), comment code,
 - Embed the need for a developer in your work - what you can achieve with those skills won't go away, value becomes embedded
 - Ed: Inspiring to see kieran's work become embedded infrastructure - how does that fit in with your developer responsibilities?
 - Kieran: try to make formerly bespoke workflows as IFI-independent - now are options
 - Sometimes ppl don't tell you they use it
 - Try to be as open & public as possible
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- Stephen: it's inspiring you work in the open! See Joanna White from MACE: she's making it happen, unafraid of saying you're not a specialist - inspiring for people
 - Kieran: Dave Rice is the role model for the profession & panel
 - Working in the open transparency brings a lot of good
 - Ed: I work in the dark. Hand tied by the institution. Wondering whether institution github must reflect institutional values.
 - Stephen: Should we make the BFI tools open? First step to make it BFI-agnostic, strip the intellectual property.
 - The answer is yes - and BFI commits
 - Evanthia: I have a Kieran (Andrew) in Victoria - how do you feel about convergence? Are you compensated for doing two jobs? Do you feel exploited?
 - Kieran: Ermmm... no.
 - Ashley: I wish developers got paid less and archivists more
 - Stephen: salary is a continuous discussion
 - Ed: imposter syndrome - how do I visualize archivist-developers in environment of "real" developers? (YouTube ref. doggie playing with bears, behaving like bears)
 - Ashley: same experience at [recurse center](#) summer retreat, trying to write codec without knowing math. I'm also that dog. Kieran: me too.
 - Somaya: combined role - multidisciplinary. What are the terms to describe ourselves? But
 - Ashley: End up doing devops.
 - Broad spectrum "technologist"
 - "Systems archivist" role at Artefactual - analyst role is essential
 - "Systems librarian" in Ireland
 - How about technical archivist or archival developer? Stephen: not everyone in my team writes code but all are technical. FIAF Technical vs cataloguing committee - cataloguing is technical!
 - Ashley: Hate the term 'digital archivist'. This is 2018

13:00 - Callie Holmes: Case Study in Open Media Adoption at the University of Georgia ([video](#), [slides](#))

- 40k students
- Newsfilm from 6 stations across Georgia, Peabody award winners
- 250'000+ physical items, mostly video
- 2012 new building

-
- No digital infra planned
 - “Nobody’s ever glanced at the LTO tapes” - “even video tapes are more appealing”

Digitization

People are important to digital archives -

- the “James” era (1995 - 2007) grant for civil rights digital lib & local tv
- the “Alex” era (shift towards open source)
 - Shift to mac, final cut
 - Hiring digital archivist
 - Scaling up & automating
 - Student research - always in hurry
 - Professional vs para-professional positions
 - Purchased a film scanner -> DPX files galore & needed storage increase
 - Collective Access introduced
 - Created open source baggage as it’s
- and now: the Callie era - fast moving train
 - Demands increased 400%
 - It’s a lot! COntlicting realities - need better workflows but no time for implementing changes

Strategies for implementing change

- Set up digital curation working group that evolved into a lib-tech-learn group at UGA libraries with listserv, monthly meeting... community of practice
 - Isn’t everything a spreadsheet in the end?
 - Developer learned python to assist this group
- Internal outsourcing
 - Difficult to let go of beautiful problems
- Challenges as opportunities
- Seize the moment - grant for peabody

Q&A

- Did you get the SAMMA files to work? Yes, with ffmpeg transcode!
- Are those LTO tapes managed? No.

- Collective Access problematic - where in config files to fix particular issues On LTO, "They're not LTFS, they're TAR, they're horrible."

- Strategy #2: Internal Outsourcing.
- Strategy #3: Challenge = Opportunity.
 - Challenges with DPX. ClamAV got false positive on some of the DPX. Submit signature to ClamAV. They changed. No longer flag.
 - J2K files from SAMMA - you can't double click it and play. Printed it out and tape it to the wall.
- Strategy #5: Lean on Y'all.
 - We need more Kieran's
 - AMIA Open Source
 - Thank you ffmpegprovisr!

Future

- FFV1/MKV for film scans: RAWcooked
- MKV Chapter feature
- Figure out how to give money to support open source projects

Q: Play SAMMA files in the end?

A: Re-transcode using ffmpeg, can play using VLC.

Q: LTO on the shelves?

A: 1 copy on shelf. Another copy at another building.

- Q: CollectiveAccess. 25% didn't setup. What are those?

A: Predecessor customised CollectiveAccess, not so easy to finish setting up. CA can handle physical and digital. Not sure whether we have the skill to make it work for us.

13:25 - Caroline Gil, Peter Oleksik: Assessing the preservation of DPX image sequences with MoMA's digital preservation ecosystem ([video](#), [slides](#))

- DPX sucks

History of the problem

- Iris Barry & history of film circulating library - collecting film since 1935, video art since 1975
- Since 1996 facility in Hamlin Pennsylvania
- Traditionally film-to-film preservation, as of 2005 DPX in the workflow for digital intermediates, transition to file output (b/c cost, labs disappearing)
- Digital repository for museum collections (DRMC), use bagit to achieve chain of custody, work with archivematica and storage through arkivum
- Lime kiln club field day - 1913, rushes assembled, film never finished
 - Scanned to dpx
 - TMS and the whole system is geared towards singular objects
- DPX breaks pipeline
 - 500 - 600 TB for DPX alone to the DRMC

Work done to grapple with it

- No consensus around handling DPX
- Unknowns around dpx as sustainable format (not self-descriptive)
- What files to keep and why
- Establishing / refining workflows

-
- Analyzing tools (MediaInfo, exiftool, imagemagick, dpx analytics, graphicsmagick) and terminology (how fields are translated from one tool to the next) - sponsored MediaInfo development for putting DPX header info to xml
 - Researched playback sw (ffplay, davinci resolve, premiere), transcoding options & packaging options
 - RAWcooked delivered 1/3 smaller files. Ran test files through Archivematica - from 4 days to 5 hours
 - Research aip store failures
 - Next steps: more testing, inc escrow retrieval from arkivum, condition assess DPX files - peer forum convened in November

Q&A

- AXF? No other implementations than what FrontPorch has

Do your DPXs have infrared channel to show damage? Not sure- next step is looking at what vendors provide - Carl would like to have them Gratitude to everyone, specifically Dave, Jerome & Kieran.

DPX sucks!

Context

MoMA Est. 1929. Film should be collected. Hired Irish Barry 1935. Film circulating department → Film department. Went around studios and convincing them that it's important to archive them. Collection including Griffith's film.

Xyz films, 1.5 mil film stills, video materials → housed at Hamland(?).

Film to film preservation. Started 1970. Photochemical+Optical continues till around mid-2000s. DPX started to come in 2005.

Film → Film

Film → DPX → Film

Film → DPX → DCP

Film → DPX → MOV + DCP

BagIt to establish chain of custody (SIP) → Archivematica (3 copies, 1 offsite (2 hours drive from Manhattan))

Work we done to address it

The challenges of DPX

- Lack of consensus in the field on the handling and/or preservation of DPX materials
- File format sustainability unknowns
- Hard to determine what to keep and why. To keep raw uncolored scans? How do we trim?

Research into DPX

- DPX is SMPTE standard. Raster. Unruly and tough to manage. Large size files. Each DPX represents a frame in a motion picture.
- Workflow: Capture decision making process within the file.
- Review FADGI guidelines <http://www.digitizationguidelines.gov/>
- Analysis of Tools: MediaInfo, Exiftool, Imagemagick, DPX analytics, GraphicsMagicks
- Analysis of terminology: how fields are translated from one tool to the next
- File header field is frequently incorrect.
- Playback, transcoding, packaging tools
- Test: MXF/OP1a, MXF/JPEG2000, FFV1/MKV → DPX and verify checksum.

- Results:

Preliminary results

1. 2K resolution DPX directory composed of 14,619 files amounted to 103.03 GB transformed into a 70.51 GB MKV using RAWcooked
2. 2K resolution DPX directory composed of 49,003 files, amounting to 616.99 GB transformed into a 210.14 GB MKV using RAWcooked
3. 2K resolution DPX directory composed of 17,525 files amounting to 145.57 GB transformed into a 50.52 GB zip directory

MOVIA

original DPX directory	# Items	size	file after transcode	size after transcode
fetisch_DPX_export_2048x858_24FPS_rec709-22_20161115	14,619	103.03 GB	fetisch_DPX_export_2048x858_24FPS_rec709-22_20161115.mkv	70.51 GB
original DPX directory	# Items	size	file after transcode	size after transcode
Friedman_Heads_Corrected_2K_DPX	49,003	616.99 GB	Friedman_Heads_Corrected_2K_DPX.mkv	210.14 GB
original DPX directory	# Items	size	file after transcode	size after transcode
Friedman_Heads_Raw_2K_DPX	35,420	445.96 GB	Friedman_Heads_Raw_2K_DPX.mkv	84.59 GB
original DPX directory	# Items	size	file after transcode	size after transcode
galerie_hd_dpx_out	17,525	145.57 GB	galerie_hd_dpx_out.zip	50.52 GB
original DPX directory	# Items	size	file after transcode	size after transcode
galerie_hd_dpx_out	17,525	145.57 GB	Bratescu-OP1A-test.mxf	32.38 GB
original DPX directory	# Items	size	file after transcode	size after transcode
NYNY	26	1.91 GB	dpx_tar_test.tar.gz	1.55 GB

- Working with Artefactual to create a separate archivematica (v1.8) pipeline exclusively for processing DPX

Next steps

- More testing incl escrow retrieval

Mike: Non-Front Porch AXF implementation. None.

Q [Carl Eugen Hoyos]: DPX files. FFmpeg dev. Does your DPX have infrared channel damages during scan?

A: Never come across. Will look into it.

Q [Carl Eugen Hoyos]: If anyone has such files, please send it to us at FFmpeg.

Someone else in the audience: I have, I will send some to you.

- Q: MXF/OP1a. What tool did you use? Re-wrapping only?
A: Yes. Re-wrap using Resolve.

13:50 - Esther Harris: Multiple Masters - case studies from the Tate Collection ([video](#), [slides](#))

dnainter.com/tools/probability16mm original destroyed when making edited masters.

Many issues. Whether pos or neg available? Facilities preferred by artists?

As a result, it is important to know what kind of work went in. Hence the diagram below.

Tina Keane - Faded Wallpaper, 1988

A lot of comparison work to figure out how were the Masters created. U-matic lo-band looks better than the 16mm print. Concludes, film has faded. Chose to restore from the 16mm film anyway because it fits the artist's original intention. Decided not to print the restored digital files back to film. Which format to present up to curator.

Slow Action - Ben Rivers, 2010

Photochemical workflow. B&W and colour both printed back to 16mm colour stock.

Family Tree diagramming tools <https://dnainter.com/tools/probability>

14:15 - Miriam Reiche: Project DELFT: Digitizing ethnological films ([video](#), [slides](#))

- “You can smell the problem” Institute for Scientific Film IWF 11.500 titles, 33k copies
 - Encyclopaedia Cinematographica
 - Films and versions accompanied by documentation
- DELFT project aim is to make films available on av.tib.eu [wonderful av portal]
- Followed FADGI and Memoria.v guidelines
- Used MWA Nova Spinner S - allows to adjust tension
 - No wetgate, diffuse light source conceals scratches somewhat
 - Wrote a mediaconch policy
- Overscan is the natural thing to do
- Contextual paper records

Questions:

- How do we save timecode in MKV? Capture as analog audio track for now.
 - Unless it's 16 or 18 fps where you have conforming issues to 24 or 25 fps
- Deinterlacing? Will soften the image and make quality worse.
- What software for digitizing betacam?
- How do you imagine giving access? Av.tib.eu when possible, but not all films can be shown freely. Collection open for ppl with research interest.

large collection of scientific films: 11'500 titles aka 33'000 copies. Founded 1952. To facilitate comparative research. Films in its entirety → encyclopaedia cinematographica.

- Film stock: 16mm B&W, colour, digibeta and documentations
- Project Goal: Each film has a DOI so that it can be referenced, unlike YouTube.
- Each digitizing project starts with the selection and description of the analogue object:
 - Filminspector RTI Pulsar
 - Date recorded for each film, archived together with the digital preservation master:
 - Info on the film cans
 - Mechanical damage
 - Vinegar syndrome
 - Shrinkage
 - Color fading direction

-
- Follow FADGI guidelines and the [Memoriav](#) recommendations.
 - QC: Mediaconch. Checked 550 films. Haven't found any technical errors.

Step 4: Quality Control

→ 7 hours Film per Week → 2TB SSD Harddrive

- Archival master ffv1/mkv
 - Derivative copy H.264/mp4 and H.265/mp4
 - Checksums framemd5
 - Technical metadata
1. Correct name of the file
 2. Content completeness: film title, film duration
 3. Image quality (artifacts etc.)
 4. Playability of the master
 5. File format validation
 6. Policy alignment
 7. Checksum check

Definition of quality

- Sustainability in the choice of digitization parameters (e.g. format, storage, etc)
- Collecting of standardized metadata
- Documentation of the source material (documenting provenance)
- Preservation of the originals
- Retaining the authenticity of the original
 - Overscan made available to user as-is. Example of books are scanned full book page, unimaginable to cut out only the text. Why is it done to pictures?
 - Know your stuff, study the materials available, choose the best and most appropriate material for restoration.
 - Additional materials contextualize the film

Q from Miriam: How to preserve the timecode, we want to preserve timecode.

A: Capture it as an analogue audio track for now.

Q: How do people watch this films?

A: AV online portal. You have to have research interest (research intent?) to watch the films.

14:40 David Pfluger: Born Compressed: Should the Preservation Community Embrace Lossy Video Compression? ([video](#), [slides](#))

- Happy to be here - happier if you're completely bored and play with my KODAK beach ball!
- See presentation #nttw2
- User view: no use for inflating compressed to uncompressed - collector of files as collector of beach balls, stored in inflated way

Technical characteristics and access hierarchy of archival files

- Storage needs to be long-term
- Born digital file should be kept as received. No reason to transcode.
- A user to the archive shouldn't have access to the master - only to the viewing elements

- Users should not be allowed to access the preservation master. Fix the access hierarchy.
- Issue:

-
- Archive receiving LTO tape with source, preservation and viewing copy all in one tape. No way to pick them out.

Memoriav recommendations: <http://memoriav.ch/recommendations-dafv-en/>

The use of lossy compression in archival masters

Q&A

- Q [Carl Eugen Hoyos]: Why would you transcode ProRes to FFV1?
- A: My level of trust in that FFV1 has identical content with my source is higher than the level of trust I have in that ProRes will continue to exist in the future.

15:25 - Helen Hockx-Yu: Media Asset Management: challenges and considerations related to balancing operational and long term archiving needs ([video](#), [slides](#))

- South Bend, Indiana - research university with catholic character. Not in France.
- Centralized media production facility
 - 2PB at present, growing really fast. Producing 500TB / year
 - [CatDV](#) was chosen after 2017 assessment project. One of the reasons, already in used by departments on campus. Britain-based company. [This is not an open source solution!]
 - Expanding CatDV's Black Pearl enterprise solution 600TB SAN - need integration
 - Spending time on business model to sustain the campus in the future
 - Based on ITIL IT Service Management principles (?)

- Video Asset Management Data Model

- Mezzanine stay for 3 months on SAN. After that goes to LTO.
 - Mezzanine format is Apple ProRes 422
- Communicating across communities: "archiving" means different things to different people ~ archiving to tape, capital 'A' archiving, university archives
- Previously: manual process to restore/write to tapes (Archiware). CatDV not aware of the location of the assets.
- Now: BlackPearl integrated into CatDV. CatDV desktop or web client → allows user to archive to tape and the Cloud directly.
- 78,000 items on physical carriers. All catalogued. Only 20%- 25% digitised → 240TB. Born-digital material → 140TB.
- Solution does not meet requirements of all campus use cases (e.g. videos used in psychology research)
- Going towards hosted Media Management solution - CatDV and 3 tiers of storage supported by [BlackPearl](#) incl. Amazon Glacier as Disaster Recovery
- 4 copies for each asset: original x 2 + mezzanine + access
- Archiving to tape used to be manual process, now managed by BlackPearl
- 600TB fills up quickly - 5TB is one football game
- Transcoding done using ffmpeg
- University Archives using Dternity as middleware instead of Archiware

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- What do DP systems do that DAMs don't?
 - Checksums to determine authenticity rather than file deduplication
 - Metadata schema building
 - File format support - transcoding down instead of equal quality
 - Challenges:
 - Still a large amount content on physical carriers
 - Retention schedule
 - How can IT support record creators and University Archives?
 - Collaboration
 - Can CatDV serve DIPs for Archives?
 - Can Archives provide guidelines re. Recording of enduring value.

Q&A

- Future direction: is there capacity to flag material for eternal retention?
 - Spoke to vendors - at API level DP system and CatDV are compatible
 - Embed metadata archive wants in CatDV
- BFI and IWM also use BlackPearl - please keep them posted about CatDV experiences
 - BlackPearl can take checksum from the MAM via REST API and use it in all its processes - CatDV should be using that
- What is the backup plan in case the Price of the license grows tenfold?
 - License is shared by users and is perpetual
 - Data can be exported to XML

15:50 - Somaya Langley: What steps to take when AV is yet to become a priority for your organisation ([video](#), [slides](#))

- DPOC formal qualifications (seem to trump experience in the UK)
- Building business cases for digipres
- 100 libraries 70 of which are connected to university
- "Born-digital - whatever that means"
- Research university → research data, PDFs, bunch of other stuff.
- Cambridge University. 600 years old - amazing manuscripts thousands years ago.
- Imaging. Spectral imaging of images.
- Priority #1: Digitised image content: 2D photography
- Priority #2:

-
- Digital archives of significant individuals or institutions.
 - Selected University records
 - Priority #3: [?]
 - Problem:
 - Funding project-based. Unable to transition to programme & BAU (Business As Usual)
 - What we've done?
 - Three-legged stool for digipres: Tech, Org, Resources.
 - Hard to do it on your own - numbers for digipres staffing
<https://www.repository.cam.ac.uk/handle/1810/271137>
 - DPC Policy Workshop Dec 4
 - How not to lose track of AV?
 - Embed it in the policy.
 - Establish an AV community of practice. Technicians, Librarians, Archivist that deal with AV materials.

16:15 - Alessandra Luciano (chair): Open Source Hustle: Callie Holmes, Kieran O'Leary, Ben Turkus, Alessandra Luciano ([video](#))

- Not WHY but HOW to open source
- Ben: successes & failures - getting NYPL to support vrecord development
 - Made business case - wrote contract in such a way that allowed looking at new possibilities
 - NYPL innovation project - open call for staff member ideas. Pool of money. "More people reading more ... captions"
 - Previously at BAVC hustled for grant money (NEH, NEA, Mellon) and enjoyed the process - difference that in current context work is small: identify little problem, talk to Dave, pitch it to superiors
 - "Just asking"
- Kieran: success & potential failure
 - Success: No effort whatsoever after work on advocating for open source support was taken into account. Walk into boss' office → Pitch → Boss nods. Support RAWcooked. Still a lot of proprietary licenses - not sure we still need so many anymore. If you

reduce your budget it will be taken away, so best to spend it differently. Got 12-bit DPX out of supporting MediaArea. Also benefited the community because it went upstream to FFmpeg as well.

- Potential fail: Want to adopt [EN 15907](#) and bought proprietary database before hearing Peter B. was working on FOSS database - missed opportunity for directing funding in more sustainable way.
- Callie: Sometimes I feel being given too much power. No one will notice what I do. Things are broken so can't get much worse.
- Ben: Making the PR case sometimes works too - demonstrate to funders that we serve community
- Alessandra: No longer side hustle. Put into policy. I might not be there in the future.
- Ben: challenge lies in working out the actual contract - boilerplate contract contains words that says rights stay with NYPL. Would be helpful to have different template for supporting open source.
- Conversation with SMPTE? Hello, Kate [Murray]! Discussions at #nttw2 to have free access at least to some SMPTE resources which relevant for the archives. Answer from Kate via Twitter: «#nttw3 hey all! I'm here in spirit. So RDD48 (formerly AS-07) is now a SMPTE RDD. And bc it is a gov product, it can/will be made publicly available at no cost.»
- Advice? Callie: Being able to point at larger institution helps.
- Ben: If you're using it, considering supporting it. Rely on it so much. It's worth the effort to support them.

Q&A

- Steve: slightly overwhelming with some FOSS projects: who goes the money to? That is very clear for proprietary projects. Avoid the contract-y stuff.
 - Carl Eugen: Kieran K should be asked about this for FFmpeg
- Somaya: technical policies. NLNZ turning guidelines into technical policies.
- Ashley: Tension with IT environment?
 - Alessandra: Force the IT guy to share office with me. Conversations. Cafeteria space always work. Leave documentations at the coffee counter. Ppl do pick up. Put posters in the bathroom. Back it up with policy and guidelines.
 - Cassie: Main dev support open source.
 - Kieran: Will never ask main IT company to handle any digipres stuff. This one guy remote in and edited my Python script.

- Find the right person in your IT department
- Ashley: IT pushback. How to handle?
 - Kieran: IT company made a comment to crack down on us.
 - Helen Hock-Yu: It's not they don't listen, but they don't understand. I spent a lot of time talking to them. What happens to the data when you retire an IT services. I want to be at the table -- IT discussion. Persistence and patience.
- Is it getting easier to hustle for FOSS?
 - Yes - conference helps, also people are tired of former unhappy experiences
 - Kieran: NTTW helped significantly.

NTTW3 Group picture - Photo credit E. Verbruggen CC-BY